

D4.2

Guidelines on methodology for extracting empirical evidence from Pilots

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D4.2/Guidelines on methodology for extracting empirical evidence from Pilots

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Abstract

This report contributes to activities related to collecting empirical evidence of dynamic feedbacks within and across the sectors analysed in the project's pilots. The key part of the report is formed by the proposed interview methodology to collect complementary information and knowledge about how dynamic interactions and feedbacks between risk drivers are perceived and understood by risk practitioners and stakeholders. An initial stocktaking of the expected insights conducted with inputs from all pilots and across workpackages (WPs) has contributed to designing the scope (research problem), structure, and design of the survey(s). The stocktaking revealed four areas of feedback sought: (1) subjective perceptions and individual judgments related to the importance of various hazards & perils and their evolution; (2) determinants of vulnerability to multi-hazards/risks; (3) performance of disaster risk reduction policies and measures; (4) questions concerning performance, deployment, and co-benefits and unintended consequences of nature-based solutions. The actual application of the methodology – i.e. performing the interviews – will be done in WP3. The insights from the interviews will feed back to WP4 and will be used in task T4.3. The guiding questions described in the report are to be contextualised and adapted to the scopes of the WP3 Pilots. It is suggested to conduct the interviews twice; with 6–9-month distance from each other, over the period from months 13 to 25 (September 2022 to September 2023). Furthermore, this and other surveys conducted for complementary scopes should be coordinated and made accessible for other research interests within and beyond this project. The common protocol should address ethical concerns, accessibility rules and principles underlying the use or re-use of the knowledge, while recognising the intellectual property rights are attributed to those who contributed to collecting and analysing the primary information.

Dissemination level of the document

- Public
- Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
- Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the European Commission Services)
- Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the European Commission Services)

Version History

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1 Introduction

Content and use of the report: This report is a result of task T4.2 which sets out the guidance to collect empirical evidence of dynamic feedbacks within and across analysed sectors. The key part of the report is the proposed structured interview methodology to collect insights from the stakeholders and societal partners engaged in the WP3 Pilots. The actual application of the methodology – i.e. performing the interviews – will be done in WP3 (task T3.4) by the pilot leads/teams. The insights from the interviews will feed back to WP4 and will be used in task T4.3. WP4 sets out to analyse empirically these feedbacks – and develop original methods and tools to this end - and to establish two-way communication with the WP3 Pilot teams which is beneficial for mutual learning.

Codesign of the report and deviation from the initial work plan: Task 4.2 started in month 10 (June 2022) and is expected to finish by month 12 (August 2022). The task kicks off the WP4 and after it is completed, the WP4 team focusses its efforts on the task T4.2 and subsequently task T4.3. The consultations related to the methodological aspects of the interview started earlier than envisaged and the WP leads and Pilot leads have been asked to indicate their expectations from the interviews. Further inputs have been collected during the General Assembly (GA) in April 2022. From the initial consultation the following suggestions emerged:

- Firstly, the stakeholders and societal partners contributing to the WP3 Pilots may not be familiar with or cognisant of the concepts and terms underlying the multi-hazard/risk (assessment and management), and therefore unable to provide insightful inputs or examples. Rather than conducting the interviews once, it appeared more useful to run two or more rounds of interviews at different times throughout the WP4 lifespan.

- Secondly, at least some of the WP3 Pilots experience a dynamic evolution and interplay of hazards, vulnerability, and exposure; either as an aftermath of the Covid-19 pandemic or as a result of structural shifts connected to Russia's war on Ukraine and/or unfolding climate risks. For example, the Veneto region is experiencing a one-in-hundred-year's drought spell impacting water and food security - already strained by the high fuel and food prices. Redesigning task 4.2 into a series of interviews is better able to capture the changes in perceptions and perceived importance of cascading risks and spill-over effects.

- Thirdly, it is envisaged that the interviews are conducted in WP3 within the context of task T3.4. However, this task only starts in the month 25, i.e. only after the task (T4.1) – which is meant to analyse the feedbacks and insights collected from across the pilots – has been completed.

Therefore, the task T42 team proposed to run the interviews (at least) twice; with 6–9-month distance from each other, over the period from months 13 to 25 (September 2022 to September 2023). The WP3 tasks T3.2 and T3.3 are better suited to contribute to implementing the interviews. No other activities are delayed or obstructed by the suggested change to the work plan, and task T4.3 will be in a position to revise the methodology before it is applied one more time. This will improve the quality of the collected insights and information.

Structure of the report: The rest of the report is structured as follows: section 2 outlines the methodology. Section 2.1 summarises early requirements collected from WP and pilot leads on what should be covered. Section 2.2. outlines the methods used consisting of a combination of online survey and in-depth interviews for the run 1. Section 2.3 summarises generic recommendations of the WP3 supporting the implementation of the interviews.

2 Guidance for survey – design, structure, and timing

2.1 Scope of survey

Task T4.2 had been designed in the description of work (DoW) to guide the collection of complementary information and knowledge from WP3 Pilots about how dynamic interactions and feedbacks between risk drivers are perceived and understood by risk practitioners and stakeholders. This also includes available empirical evidence which would otherwise not be available to the MYRIAD-EU team. For the purpose of this report, risk factors & drivers are understood as any attribute, characteristic, or variable which causes or determines the risk, or amplifies the levels of risk. In more practical terms, the scope of this task is to collect any information about the dynamic interactions of factors that drive the vulnerability and resilience of households, businesses, and other valuable assets to natural hazards. The scope of the task is intentionally broad to cover any aspects of the pilot-driven research that may be important for the project.

At the onset of the task's implementation, we have collected an inventory of expectations on task T4.2 from across the various work packages (WPs) and Pilots. This initial stocktaking of the expected insights has contributed to designing the scope (research problem), structure, and design of the survey(s). These expectations have been collected throughout the months 5-9 and discussed during the General Assembly 2022 in Vienna.

The results of the stocktaking exercise revealed the following four areas for which insights from the project's pilots are sought:

- (1) subjective perceptions and individual judgments related to the importance of various hazards & perils in the pilot area, individually or in combination, and their evolution over the past decades,
- (2) determinants of vulnerability and how multiple concomitant or consecutive hazard strikes contribute to observed vulnerability levels,
- (3) performance of disaster risk reduction policies and measures, in particular their cross-border and -sectoral effects,
- (4) questions related to performance, deployment, and co-benefits and unintended consequences of nature-based solutions.

The first area of feedback sought from the surveys refers to how hazard (perils) and risks are perceived and what importance is attributed to them – individually and in combination. Perceptions of risk, risk attitudes, and behaviour play an important role in building societal preparedness to, and resilience against natural hazards. Perceptions of risk are shaped by knowledge and experience, personality traits, spiritual beliefs, cultural and environmental context, and a host of other factors such as age, gender, social networks, and media. Risk perception studies are often conducted in specific local or regional contexts. Large-scale studies have been conducted by Eurobarometer, European Values Study (EVS), and European Social Survey (ESS)¹. Modern computational social science methods make it possible to assimilate behavioural aspects of human decision-making in risk analysis, assessment, and communication. These methods can leverage the knowledge about social behaviour and contribute to improving disaster risk management policies and practices (Conte et al., 2012). In the context of task T4.2, the expected insights include more anecdotal information about how the interviewees perceive the changes in spatial and temporal patterns and hazard(s) manifestation and magnitudes of observed impacts. Emphasis is placed on simultaneous or consecutive multi-hazard/peril strikes.

¹ Eurobarometer entails regular (bi-annual) and irregular (special) surveys conducted by the European Commission across all Member States. EVS (europeanvaluesstudy.eu) is large-scale, cross-national, repeated cross-sectional survey research programme on basic human values, providing insights into the ideas, beliefs, preferences, attitudes, values and opinions of citizens. ESS (www.europeansocialsurvey.org) is a cross-national survey measuring attitudes, beliefs and behaviour patterns using face-to-face interviews.

The second areas of expected insights refer to vulnerability to consecutive (including cascading) or concurrent (including compound) hazard strikes (Drakes and Tate, 2022). The vulnerability in multi-hazard can be determined by the co-existence and interactions among different elements at risk (e.g. population, infrastructure, cultural heritage, ecosystems, etc.) or by vulnerability conditions changing over time (e.g. changes in socio-economic conditions, increase of vulnerability due to the occurrence of a sequence of hazardous events on the same system). Multi-risk assessment analyses the interrelated effects that multiple hazards can have on the vulnerable sectors and elements at risk. For example, a flood can trigger a landslide damaging critical infrastructures (e.g., water and power network, roads/railways) and consequently the access to relevant services for the society (energy and water supply, emergency services); a combination of rainfall and storm surge can lead to a compound event requiring the simultaneous management of flood risk in coastal and river plains; a region hit by several consecutive hazards, may face an amplification of risks due to increased vulnerability (and reduced adaptive capacity) conditions after each individual event. A separate but connected set of questions refer to how multi-hazard/risk management scheme address those most vulnerable and at risk of poverty and social exclusion. The international and European disaster risk reduction and climate adaptation agendas place emphasis just resilience – i.e. ensuring that risk management is responsive to those most in need.

The third area refers to disaster risk management policies and measures, and the cross-policy/sectoral interactions (including positive spillover effects and unintended negative consequences). Policy coherence stands for coherence between policies addressing all dimensions of risk management, including synergies and benefits across economic, social, and environmental policy areas (e.g., climate change adaptation and disaster risk reduction), balancing domestic policy objectives with internationally recognised goals, and addressing transboundary and long-term impacts of policies, including those likely to affect developing countries. The IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (AR6) (Ara Begum et al., 2022; Möller et al., 2022) paid attention to maladaptation² and unintended consequences of policy responses. Better understanding of and full account of multi-hazard/risk interactions can avoid maladaptive strategies. For example, fuel reduction by targeted burning of bushland and leaf litter can reduce forest fire risk and intensity of subsequent fires but also increase soil erosion and hence amplify flood and landslide risks (Rusk et al., 2022). The AR6 also anticipates that in the future, the established risks (propeller) framework consisting of hazard, vulnerability and exposure will be extended by including the risk arising from unintended consequences of risk responses.

The fourth area of feedback south through the task T4.2 refers to nature-based solutions (NbS). These are defined as 'inspired and supported by nature, which are cost-effective, simultaneously provide environmental, social and economic benefits and help build resilience' (Calliari et al., 2019; IUCN, 2020). NbS can provide means to regulate GHG in the atmosphere, mitigating climate hazard risks - through mass stabilisation, water flow regulation, wind dissipation, and temperature regulation - removing particle pollution and improving air quality, protecting soil and biodiversity, and enhancing climate resilience (Griscom et al., 2017). Compared to engineered, built or fossil-based solutions, NbS approaches may be cost-effective and have many ecological, social, and economic benefits. However, despite mounting evidence of their technical efficacy, NbS face sizeable challenges and barriers to adoption, which - depending on the contexts - may include poor adaptation to given socio-cultural situations, possible ecosystem disservices (von Döhren and Haase, 2015), absence of supportive governance and financial instruments to stimulate implementation, low social acceptance, limited business innovation, and failure to account for the true social value of the generated benefits (Venkataramanan et al., 2020). In some cases, NbS can also further

² Defined as “actions that may lead to increased risk of adverse climate-related outcomes, including via increased greenhouse gas emissions, increased or shifted vulnerability to climate change, more inequitable outcomes, or diminished welfare, now or in the future. Most often, maladaptation is an unintended consequence”

amplify, rather than reduce, urban vulnerabilities and inequalities, by contributing to gentrification (Bockarjova et al., 2020; Haase et al., 2017).

2.2 Methodology

2.2.1 Methods

Interviews are a common and frequently used survey method in qualitative research to elicit information (opinions or beliefs) and insights (e.g. practice examples) (Hamill, 2014). There are many ways interviews can be carried out, either face-to-face or in small groups, in spontaneous or formal conversations or in structured, closed interview form. The latter is more similar to questionnaires, which are also frequently used for similar scope.

There are numerous methodological guides on how to use and implement interviews, such as Brinkmann and Kvale (2014) who suggest that interviewing is not merely a method but a series of skills and crafts. One or more interviewers guide the conversation, and one or more interviewees answer them. In its most fundamental form, an interview is a mutual learning exercise of a “contextually bound story” (Fontana and Frey, 2005). The mutual construction is a result of the interviewers’ guidance and the interviewee’s perspective of what is relevant in the context of the posed question. Although interviews are commonly applied in disaster risk research, we are not aware of any recent review article systematically analysing how and why interviews have been used across the different themes related to disaster risk reduction (DRR). Contrary to this, Young et al. (2018) have conducted a similar comprehensive review of how interviews are used in (nature) conservation research.

The form of interviews may range from structured/closed to completely open-ended, but the most preferred form is the semi-structured one. The structured interview employs closed-ended questions, with binary or multiple answers and the questions are posed in the same order for all interviewees. In an unstructured or informal interview, the interviewers let interviewees expand on their views in what is close to a natural conversation. Semi-structured interviews are a combination of both: the interviewers use a set of guiding questions but preserve the flexibility of the conversation.

Compared to individual interviews, involving one interviewee at a time, group interviews (or focus groups) involve several interviewees simultaneously who are interacting between themselves. Group interviews are popular because interviewees can build upon, respond to, or be otherwise stimulated by the responses of others, hence offering more thoughtful and in-depth insights (Betts et al., 1996). However, group interviews require balancing the opinions of the participants to avoid bias introduced by dominant or opinionated interviewees.

Careful planning of interviews includes formulation sampling of interviewees, i.e. choice of who should be interviewed and how many participants are needed to appropriately answer the research questions. Given the exploratory purpose of the T4.2 survey, the WP3 Pilots may choose how many interviewees to involve. This also involves a trade-off between the insights sought as a complementary source of information for other work packages, and the work intensity in the WP3 itself. However, in section 2.3 we recommend conducting at least 8-10 individual or 2-3 group interviews to meet the project requirements.

Unlike interviews, **questionnaires** are answered by respondents without the interviewer(s) (also called surveyors or pollsters) being present. The questions are written and may be closed or open-ended (allowing free answers for explanation of the previous answers) but their order cannot be changed. Respondents have more time to prepare answers, this is why questionnaires are more suited to collect analytical information.

Various forms of surveys are entailed in expert elicitation (processes), defined as systematic consultation of experts on subjects characterised by uncertainties of any kind, including diverging views & perspectives and lack of data. Expert elicitation is also used in qualitative studies aimed at converging views on semantic definitions, assumptions or conceptual (cause-effect) models (Knol et al., 2010). Structured elicitation protocols have helped to

reduce survey biases and improve the accuracy and transparency of the resulting judgements (Knol et al., 2010). In-depth expert elicitation is not the primary scope of this task.

2.2.2 Guidance

The process of designing surveys includes various steps, including

- a. definition/refining research questions,
- b. choosing type and form of the method,
- c. drafting and testing the guiding questions (including their ethical review),
- d. sampling the interviewees,
- e. implementing the survey and analysing the results.

1. Definition of the research questions. The surveys designed in the task T42 serve primarily to **screen** – rather than systematically investigate distributions of – the views and perspectives on dynamic feedbacks within and across the sectors analysed in the project’s pilots. The collected insights are anecdotal instances of dynamic feedbacks, rather than a systematic collection, taxonomy or typology, and in-depth analysis. However, the WP3 Pilot team may refine the scope and increase the level of ambition – up to conducting a tailored expert elicitation exercise as a follow up of the initial exploratory survey. This is useful in cases the surveys are used also to explore on specific recent event or prospected hypothetical event scenario.

2. Choosing type and form of the survey method. The form of survey which is closest to the scope of the exploratory survey is the interview. However, the WP3 teams can combine questionnaires reaching out a wider audience within the stakeholders’ organisations prior to choosing the interviewees or combine the WP3 workshops with group interviews/focus groups to create an inspiring environment in which the participants are motivated by and interact with other stakeholders. In any case, the WP3 teams should prepare reporting schemes summarising the insights collected according to the guiding questions.

3. Drafting and testing the guiding questions. The guiding questions prepared based on the expectations from across project’s WPs and described hereafter will need to be contextualised in the WP3 Pilots and adapted to the specific scope. Furthermore, the survey will need to be coordinated with other surveys planned or already implemented within and across pilot areas. Therefore, the guiding questions need to be understood as generic and adaptable schemes.

Codes	Thematic areas and sub-topics/questions
A.	Salience of multi-hazard/multi-peril risks
A1	How important are the following hazards [/in your pilot area/organisation]: landslides, volcanic eruptions, heavy rainfall, wildfire, and droughts?
A2	Do you believe [/observe or sense] there is a systematic trend in hazard manifestations and their impacts [/ in economic, social, or environmental terms] over time?
A2.1	How important are the following factors – climate change, land use/urban expansion in hazard-prone areas, lack of multi-hazard risk assessments [/scenarios], and others (please explain)?
A3	What combinations of simultaneous or consecutive hazard & peril strikes do you feel are getting more important to inform (disaster) risk management [/ in your organisation] [/ in the context of your work]?
A3.1	Are the impacts and/or policy targets used to monitor the performance of risk management schemes addressing combinations of hazards the same as in the case of single hazards?
B.	Vulnerability to multi-hazard/multi-peril risks
B1	What attributes characterise (social, economic, ecosystem) vulnerability to hazards/perils [/do you consider the most important]?

B2	Can you name examples of situations in which vulnerability conditions changed substantially in the case of simultaneous or consecutive hazard & peril strikes?
B3	Do you believe that people at risk of poverty or social exclusion [/with lower income, living in poverty] are more likely to live in areas prone to natural hazards?
B3.1	Is there any evidence of people at risk of poverty having moved to more hazard-prone areas or do you expect that this may happen? If so, what makes you believe this may happen and what sources of information may underpin these trends?
B4	To what extent do you believe the risk management schemes [/in your pilot/organisation/context in which you work] are accountable to ethical and solidarity principles?
B4.1	Can you describe in your own words what just or equitable resilience is, how it can be promoted and to what extent the underpinning principles have been implemented in the risk management practice [/in your pilot/organisation/context in which you work]?
C. Disaster risk reduction policies and measures	
C1	Can you name examples [/and evidence] of cases when addressing one hazard/risk (1) created positive effects or conditions for reducing other hazard/risks; (2) undermined efforts meant to reduce hazard risks in other places [/sectors] or managing other types of hazards/perils?
C1.1	Are these co-benefits or unintended effects recognised and addressed in risk governance [/policies] and systematically promoted (in case of co-benefits) or avoided (in case of unintended consequences)? Is the evidence of these effects systematically collected, analysed and reported? If so, are the governance arrangement responsive to such evidence?
C1.2	have you experienced in your sector [/policy area] collateral benefits or unintended consequences of policies implemented in other areas/sectors?
C2	Do you believe that risk management choices related to addressing some hazards (or combination thereof) create tensions or even conflicts across policy areas/sectors? Can you name examples of similar conflicts?
C2.1	Does you believe that multi-hazard/risk management schemes can exacerbate these tensions/conflicts?
C3	Are people with a lower income or living in poverty getting help through specific funds to increase resilience or for post-disaster recovery?
D. Nature-based solutions for reducing disaster risk	
D1	Can you name examples of nature-based solutions (NbS) that effectively contribute to reducing disaster risk caused by individual hazard perils (especially droughts, heatwaves and wildfires) or any combination of thereof?
D2	For the examples of NbS that you mentioned, can you name potential co-benefits or negative effects (disbenefits) and have these been considered when adopting/implementing the solutions?
D2.1	Are the co-benefits and disservices (or unintended consequences) systematically assessed, monitored and corrected with supplementary policy interventions or measures?
D3	Are NbS systematically promoted in your pilot [/organisation, /policy area or sector]

Sampling the interviewees. Choosing the ‘right’ stakeholders and experts are important for the success and quality of the survey. Starting from the organisations (stakeholders and societal partners) already mobilised and engaged in the pilot-driver research & innovation, the suggested methods to identify the interviewees is the snowball sampling. This is a

nonprobability sampling methods where previously interviewed stakeholders suggest recruiting of other subjects from among their acquaintances. The sample size of the survey depends on the survey form and specific scope within the WP3 pilot work flow. As a benchmark, the suggested size is 15-20 for online or printed questionnaires, 7-10 for semi-structures interviews and 2-3 groups interviews with 3-5 participants in each.

Implementing the survey and analysing the results. A good understanding of the project goal and working method – hence contextualisation of the survey - is a prerequisite of a successful survey. The survey's participants should be introduced to the project's expected outcomes, including to what the insights from the survey will be used for. It is also important to explain what is meant by multi-hazard/risk interactions & dynamics, in simple words and using examples that are accessible and familiar to the participants. The results should be codified using the codes. WP4 will conduct a training session on implementing the survey and collecting/analysing the results. It is recommended to conduct the survey in two rounds with 6–9-month distance from each other, over the period from months 13 to 25 (September 2022 to September 2023).

2.3 Recommendations

Planning for the interviews in the WP3 pilots. The survey guided by the task T4.2 is but one of many surveys to be implemented in the WP3 Pilots and elsewhere in the project. Each pilot team is recommended to develop a draft plan of surveys and schedule their implementation in the most useful way to inform the pilot related assessment – while providing feedbacks to other part of the MYRIAD-EU project. The surveys will build upon and contribute to reinforcing relationships – and mutual learning - between the team members and pilot study stakeholders. Next scheduled surveys involving experts and stakeholders who participated in earlier surveys will be able to build upon better understanding of the multi-hazard/risk terms and the purpose/methods applied through the project. Therefore, the first or earlier surveys can allocate more time to building a shared understanding of what multiple concurrent and consecutive hazard strikes, why they are important and how these can be managed. It is useful to keep a track record on topics on which the participants have been interviewed and their previous engagement in or familiarity with the project.

Comparability and re-usability of the survey's results. The surveys implemented in the WP3 pilots need to be put in the context of the research and innovation pursued in the specific context, while collecting feedbacks and contextual insights for research & innovation activities elsewhere in the MYRIAD-EU project. However, the surveys are time consuming and require sizeable efforts. A closely coordinated implementation can save time and resources and provide input for comparative analysis and assessment. It is important therefore that (i) surveys are implemented using a common but flexible protocol, (ii) all anonymised interviews are recorded and transcribed – or otherwise summarised – and (iii) made accessible to other researchers and research purposes within the project. The common/structured protocol should ensure addressing ethical concerns (how to preserve anonymity and confidentiality, ensure equal participation, and capture views and perspectives of disadvantaged/special concern social groups), accessibility and retrievability rules and principles underlying the use or re-use of the knowledge, while recognising the intellectual property rights are attributed to those who contributed to collecting and analysing the primary information. Moreover, MYRIAD-EU collaborates with various other European RTD projects with similar or complementary scopes. The knowledge obtained from the WP3 surveys can contribute to existing knowledge base or complement future surveys (or meta-surveys) conducted at a large scale and across various research & innovation initiatives. **We suggest that a project-wide inventory of past and planned surveys is centrally managed across all WPs of the project.**

Choice of the survey methods. The section 2.2.1 introduced several techniques of qualitative research surveys – questionnaire, individual and group interviews. The latter are similar to and can be combined with – or implemented as a part of – other WP3 workshops. Each of the method has specific advantages and disadvantages and are unequally suited for a specific purpose or time step of the pilot-related research. These advantages and disadvantages

need to be weighted when designing specific survey. Questionnaires are less time consuming and ensure full anonymity of the respondents, but the responses may be too short to allow for a deeper understanding of respondents' views and experiences. Interviews are time consuming but allow for a richer feedback and greater control of the data collection process. All survey methods rely on participants' willingness or motivation to respond, which may also be shaped by phrasing of questions or who is posing them. Semantic differences and biases can be controlled by posing the same question multiple times and in different forms (using different words). Group interviews allow for opinions and views of respondents being shaped also by the views expressed by their peers. A combination of methods is likely to deliver better results. **The explanatory character of the surveys covered in task T4.2 and this report is probably best served by combinations of pre- and post-workshop surveys, brainstorming break out/focus groups and in-depth interviews in selected experts who are deeply familiar with the aim of the project and the nature of multi-hazard/risks.**

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